

Separation of selected 4f and 5f metals by solid phase extraction : A review

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Abstract : This paper reviews the solid phase extraction of selected 4f and 5f metals reported by various researchers during the last decade. It is seen that major work has been carried out on uranium and thorium. This literature survey presents in a nutshell the characterization and different parameters for effectiveness of the solid phase extractants, which has been applied for separation of uranium, thorium and lanthanides in different matrices. A discussion of analytical methodologies, applications and analytical characteristics has also been included.

Keywords : Solid phase extraction, uranium, thorium, lanthanide separation, review.

Introduction

Analytical procedures for separation are widely used in mineral exploration, geology and geochemistry, material science, nuclear industry and so on. Among analytical scale separations of lanthanides and actinides the most widely used methods are ion exchange and liquid chromatography. There are only a few reviews on solid phase extraction published in recent years¹⁻³. The most useful column chromatographic techniques that have been applied for separation are adsorption and partition chromatography, ion-pair chromatography, cation exchange chromatography and capillary electrophoresis etc.

Solid phase extraction⁴⁻⁶ is of major concern in trace metal analysis. These extractants serve mainly two important purposes viz. toxicity estimation, recovery of valuable metal ions. In the past, liquid-liquid extraction technique was the most widely adopted method for this process, especially in case of recovery of radioactive nuclides from acidic nuclear spent fuel systems. In spite of its extensive usage, the major limitations of this technique are its labour intensiveness, cost effectiveness and potential explosive hazards due to third phase formation. Moreover, severe environmental pollution is encountered due to finite solubility of the extractants, solvents and modifiers in the aqueous phase. Therefore, in order to overcome these limitations and to encourage solvent free extraction, environment friendly chelating polymers have grown significantly².

In recent years, the use of chelating polymers⁷⁻⁹ which can be said to be a hybrid of liquid extraction

and ion-exchange techniques, featuring characteristics like high ion-selectivity, environment friendly, simplicity, low cost and time conservation, has been the most preferred method for the process of metal ion extraction. The initially developed chelating polymers, tailored with a variety of organic ligands, were ion-selective but possessed moderate exchange kinetics, poor metal loading capacity and much more their synthetic routes were quite tedious. These limitations were mainly attributed to the poor hydrophilic character of the resin matrix, which is a crucial factor in the process of metal ion extraction. But despite these drawbacks, the use of chelating resins can be considered as a better alternative to the existing conventional methods.

The separation of actinides from various waste materials is a significant problem faced by researchers³. The threat arises not only because of the potential long-term hazard of many of the actinides, but also due to the regulatory requirements associated with actinide waste disposal, which are different from those with other radioactive wastes. Similar problems exist for waste produced in the past as a result of nuclear weapons production programs and wastes likely to be produced in the future emerging from operations required for waste disposal. Hence it is no doubt a challenging task for analytical chemists to quantitatively recover these trace actinide metal ions.

The lanthanides, due to their similarity, serve as a particularly suitable group of indicator elements. The determination of these in other materials is also of in-

terest. The presence of trace quantities of lanthanides in high purity metals, semiconductors and glasses have important influences on the electrical, magnetic, mechanical, nuclear and optical properties¹⁰.

Uranium, thorium and lanthanides are important metals not only from the view point of industrial applications but also for tackling energy and environmental problems. Uranium and thorium find extensive application as nuclear fuel in power plants and their main sources are pitchblende, monazite sand and sea water. The separation of these economically important metal ions is also a matter of concern as the nuclear waste coming out of reactors cause serious and irreversible environmental and biological damages¹¹. Both the metal ions are known to cause acute toxicological effects in mammals and their compounds are potential occupational carcinogens¹². Uranium is an important element whose isotopes occur in various concentrations and its most prominent oxidation state in radioactive waste and geological materials being U^{VI}.

Currently, the great interest in uranium arises from its known toxicity and the possibility of human exposure to it. Uranium and its compounds are highly toxic which cause progressive or irreversible renal injury and in acute cases may lead to kidney failure and death. The tolerable intake of uranium established by WHO based on Gilman's studies is 0.6 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ of body weight

per day. The maximum permissible uranium concentration in drinking water as per WHO, Health Canada and Australian drinking water guidelines is 9, 20 and 20 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ¹³⁻¹⁵. Uranium has been largely extracted selectively by liquid-liquid extraction^{16,17}.

Direct toxicity of thorium is low due to its stability at ambient temperatures; however, thorium powder is self-ignitable to thorium oxide¹⁸, which is toxic. Again, thorium nitrate in living organisms is mainly localized in liver, spleen and marrow and it precipitates in hydroxide form¹⁹, which is carcinogenic to living organisms.

Separation of 4f and 5f metals from different matrices has always been a challenge to analytical chemists. So in this work we have tried to outline the extraction behaviour of several solid phase extractants towards uranium, thorium and some lanthanides, their synthetic procedures, nature of ligating sites, influence of pH on the uptake of metal ions and methods of detection. Fields of applications, analytical characteristics have also been surveyed.

Characterization of solid phase extractants

Synthetic procedures :

Chelating polymers presented in Table 1²⁰⁻⁹⁸ are made of two components : inert solid support, chelating ligand moiety. The incorporation of ligand moiety

Table 1. A survey of functional groups incorporated onto polymeric support and extraction of metal ions

Sl. no.	Functional group	Polymeric support	Metal ions studies	Ref. no.
1.	4-(2-Thiazolylazo)resorcinol (TAR)	Amberlite XAD-16	La ^{III} , Gd ^{III} , Yb ^{III} , U ^{VI}	20
2.	1-(2-Thiazolylazo)-2-naphthol (TAN)	Amberlite XAD-16	Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	21
3.	Tiron	Amberlite XAD-16	U ^{VI}	22
4.	Quinalizarin	Amberlite XAD-16	U ^{VI}	23
5.	(Bis-3,4-dihydroxybenzyl)- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine	Amberlite XAD-16	Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	24
6.	2-(2-Thiazolylazo)-5-dimethylaminophenol (TAM)	Amberlite XAD-16	Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	25
7.	<i>N,N</i> -Dibutyl- <i>N'</i> -benzoylthiourea (DBBT)	Amberlite XAD-16	U ^{VI}	26
8.	[2-(1-Methyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1 <i>H</i> -pyrazol-4-ylcarbamoyl)-ethyl]phosphinic acid (MOPPA)	Amberlite XAD-16	La ^{III} , Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	27
9.	<i>N,N</i> -Diethylcarbamoylmethylphosphonic acid	Amberlite XAD-16	La ^{III} , Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	28
10.	(Bis-2,3,4-trihydroxybenzyl)ethylenediamine	Amberlite XAD-16	Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	29
11.	3,4-Dihydroxybenzoylmethylphosphonic acid	Amberlite XAD-16	Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	30
12.	(Bis-2-hydroxybenzyl)- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine	Amberlite XAD-16	U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV}	31
13.	<i>p</i> -Amino- <i>N,N</i> -diethylacetamide (ADHA)	Amberlite XAD-16	U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV}	32
14.	[(2-Dihydroxyarsinoylphenylamino)-methyl]phosphonic acid	Amberlite XAD-16	U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV} , La ^{III}	33

15.	Oxyacetoneacetamide	Amberlite XAD-16	U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV}	34
16.	<i>o</i> -Vanillinsemicarbazone	Amberlite XAD-4	La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	35
17.	Succinic acid	Amberlite XAD-4	U ^{VI}	36
18.	4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide	Amberlite XAD-4	U ^{VI}	37
	2,6-Diacetylpyridine			
	2,3-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde			
	2-Thiophene carboxaldehyde			
19.	Bicine	Amberlite XAD-4	La ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Tb ^{III} , Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	38
20.	Octacarboxymethyl- <i>C</i> - methylcalix[4]resorcinarene	Amberlite XAD-4	U ^{VI}	39
21.	2,6-Diacetylpyridine	Amberlite XAD-4	U ^{VI}	40
22.	Humic acid	Amberlite XAD-4	Th ^{IV}	41
23.	Malonic acid	Amberlite XAD-4	Th ^{IV}	42
24.	Bis-2-[(<i>o</i> -carbomethoxy)phenoxy]ethylamine	Amberlite XAD-4	La ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Sm ^{III}	43
25.	<i>p</i> -Tert-butylcalix[8]arene	Amberlite XAD-4	Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	44
26.	5-Aminoquinoline-8-ol	Amberlite XAD-4	U ^{VI}	45
27.	Pyrogallol	Amberlite XAD-2	U ^{VI}	46
28.	Thorin	Amberlite XAD-7	Sm ^{III} , Eu ^{III} , Gd ^{III}	47
29.	4-Ethoxy-4-ethyl- <i>N,N</i> -bis-2- ethylhexylbutanamide (EEBEHBA)	Merrifield chloromethylated resin	U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV} , La ^{III} , Nd ^{III}	48
30.	Di-bis(2-ethylhexyl)- malonamide	Merrifield chloromethylated styrene-divinylbenzene	Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	49
31.	Quinoline-8-ol	Merrifield chloromethylated styrene-divinylbenzene	U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV} , La ^{III}	50
32.	Phosphoric acid	Poly(glycidylmethylacrylate- <i>co</i> -divinylbenzene)	U ^{VI}	51
33.	Thenoyltrifluoroacetone (TTA)	Merrifield chloromethylated resin	Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	52
34.	2,2'-Dihydroxyazobenzene	Chloromethylated polystyrene	U ^{VI}	53
35.	6,6,6-Trifluoro-2,5-dioxo-4- (thiophene-2-carbonyl)hexyl- phosphinic acid (TDHCHPA)	Amberlite XAD-16	U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV} , Nd ^{III} , La ^{III}	54
36.	Azobenzylphosphonic acid	PS-DVB	U ^{VI}	55
37.	Methylene phosphonic acid Resorcinol arsonic acid Duolite ES 467	Polystyrene formaldehyde copolymer	U ^{VI}	56
38.	Calix[4]arene- <i>o</i> -vanillinsemicarbazone	Merrifield chloromethylated resin	La ^{III} , U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV}	57
39.	Calix[6]arene hydroxamic acid	Poly(styrene- β - hydroxylamine)	Ce ^{IV} , Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	58
40.	Calix[4]arene semicarbazone	Polymer support	La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	59
41.	<i>N,N'</i> -Ethylenemono-(3-carboxysalicylideneimine) Mono(salicylideneimine)	Chloromethylated polystyrene	U ^{VI}	60
42.	Polyacetatepolyamine	Silica gel	Eu ^{III}	61
43.	Serine	Chitosan	U ^{VI}	62

Table-1 (contd.)

44.	Serine diacetic acid	Chitosan	Th ^{IV}	63
45.	3,4-Dihydroxy benzoic acid	Chitosan	U ^{VI}	64
46.	2-Amino-5-hydroxy benzoic acid	Chitosan	U ^{VI} , Y ^{III} , La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Pr ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Sm ^{III} , Eu ^{III} , Gd ^{III} , Tb ^{III} , Dy ^{III} , Ho ^{III} , Er ^{III} , Tm ^{III} , Yb ^{III} , Lu ^{III}	65
47.	Cross linked dicholoro carbonyl spacer chitosan (CRC) Cross linked carbonyl spacer chitosan (CRCH)	Chitosan	U ^{VI}	66
48.	Quinoline-8-ol	Cellulose	Th ^{IV}	67
49.	Bis(2-ethylhexyl)methanediphosphonic	Acrylic ester	Nd ^{III} , Th ^{IV} , U ^{VI}	68
50.	Diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA)	Phenol-formaldehyde copolymer	La ^{III} , Th ^{IV}	69
51.	Propylenediaminetetraacetic acid (PDTA)	Crosslinked glycidylmetha- crylate gel (GMA gel)	La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Pr ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Sm ^{III} , Eu ^{III} , Gd ^{III} , Tb ^{III} , Dy ^{III} , Ho ^{III} , Er ^{III} , Tm ^{III} , Yb ^{III} , Lu ^{III}	70
52.	Phenol based resins	Polycondensation of formaldehyde	Eu ^{III}	71
53.	Phenol/Resorcinol	Formaldehyde-condensed azo dyes of aniline and 4,4'- diaminodiphenylmethane	U ^{VI}	72
54.	Tannin	Epoxy resin	La ^{III} , Y ^{III}	73
55.	Acyl-hydroxy-pyrazole	Silica	Eu ^{III}	74
56.	Anthranilic acid	Guaran	U ^{VI}	75
57.	Amidoxime	Poly(acrylamidoxime)	U ^{VI}	76
58.	5,7-Dichloroquinoline-8-ol	Naphthalene	U ^{VI}	77
59.	Dicyclohexano-18-crown-6	Benzophenone	U ^{VI}	78
60.	1-(2-Pyridylazo)-2-naphthol	Benzophenone	U ^{VI}	79
61.	Polyhydroxamic acid	Polyacrylamide	U ^{VI}	80
62.	<i>N,N,N',N'</i> -Tetramethylmalonamide (TMMA)	Polystyrene	Ce ^{III} , Eu ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Dy ^{III} , U ^{VI}	81
63.	Iminodiacetate	Chelex-100	U ^{VI}	82
64.	Iminodiacetate	Chelex-100	La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Pr ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Sm ^{III} , Eu ^{III} , Gd ^{III} , Tb ^{III} , Dy ^{III} , Ho ^{III} , Er ^{III} , Tm ^{III} , Yb ^{III} , Lu ^{III}	83
65.	Iminodiacetate (CCS-HP/IDA)	Chitopearl CI-03	La ^{III}	84
66.	Iminodiacetate	Metpac cc-1 (Dionex)	U ^{VI}	85
67.	Iminodiacetate	Tulsion CH-90	Eu ^{III} , U ^{VI}	86
68.	Iminodiacetate	IDA-type chelating resin disk	U ^{VI}	87
69.	Sulphonated azo dyes	Anion exchange resin	U ^{VI}	88
70.	8-Hydroxyquinoline (8-HQ)	Fluorinated metal alkoxide glass	U ^{VI}	89
71.	Amidoxime	Fibrous and polymeric adsorbent	U ^{VI}	90
72.	Tri- <i>n</i> -octyl-phosphine oxide (TOPO)	Silica membrane discs	U ^{VI}	91
73.	Catechol	Silica gel	U ^{VI}	92

Table-1 (contd.)

74.	Diarylazobisphenol	Activated carbon	U ^{VI}	93
75.	Hydroxylamine	Poly(acrylonitrile-co-divinylbenzene)	U ^{VI}	94
76.	Poly(amidoxime-hydroxamic acid) resins	-	La ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Sm ^{III} , Gd ^{III} , Tb ^{III}	95
77.	Persimmon tannin	Glutaraldehyde	U ^{VI} , Th ^{IV}	96
78.	Ethyl hexyl phosphonic acid	Polyurethane foam	Th ^{IV}	97
79.	Poly(8-hydroxyquinoline-5,7-dimethylene)	Bisphenol-A	La ^{III} , Ce ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Sm ^{III} , Gd ^{III}	98

can be carried out either by physical adsorption that is impregnation to the solid support or by chemical modification, which is known as anchoring. It is seen that impregnated resins have higher adsorption capacity. But they are less preferred ones due to their tendency to undergo ligand bleeding on subsequent usage. It is generally acknowledged that the resins prepared by covalent bonding of a ligand to the copolymer backbone tend to be more chemically stable to acidic eluants than those resins prepared by impregnation. Hence these can extract metal ions in the specific pH range along with extraction of actinides in strong acid media when required.

In case of chemically modified chelating resin synthesis nearly all workers have used classical methods of synthesis. Only in case of bis-2-[(*o*-carbomethoxy)phenoxy]ethylamine⁴³ anchored on to XAD-4 has been synthesized using a facile, time saving microwave-assisted process.

Donor atoms at the active site :

Lanthanides are hard acids bonding preferentially to the hard base ligands like O and N. If we take a look at the functional groups (Table 1) impregnated/anchored onto the organic polymers, it can be easily seen that atoms like O, N, S and P donor atoms are present in general. In solvent extraction procedure organo phosphorous extractants like tributyl phosphate (TBP), trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO), carbamoyl methyl phosphonic acid (CMPO) etc., were used for actinide extraction. But these had a tendency to undergo faster radiolytic degradation. Since recovery of lanthanides and actinides from high level radioactive wastes is a major concern these had to be substituted. Thus high molecular weight *N,N'*-dialkyl aliphatic amides came out to be better alternatives. It was also found that branched substituted diamides could be used to separate actinides from lanthanides. But finite aqueous phase solubility and third phase formation were the inherent drawbacks of this technique. Solid phase extraction overcomes these limita-

tions and it is seen that often ligands same/similar to those very extractants have been used and anchored/impregnated on to polymeric support to obtain novel chelating resins for actinide/lanthanide extraction/separation. In case of Amberlite XAD-16-[2-(1-methyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-ylcarbamoyl)ethyl]-phosphinic acid (MOPPA), Raju *et al.*²⁷ have synthesized 4-acrylamido antipyrone from 4-amino antipyrone (as it is known that 4-amino antipyrone derivatives form coordination complexes with lanthanides) and successfully anchored onto phosphinic acid polymer. The phosphinic acid, amide carbonyl ligand moieties contribute to the resins selectivity towards actinides even at high acidities. The hydrophilic hydroxyl and antipyrone moieties enhance the metal ion accessibility into the polymer matrix, thereby significantly improving the kinetics. In low acidic conditions the antipyrone ring also significantly participates in the extraction process, thereby, exhibiting extraction for lanthanides also. In (bis-3,4-dihydroxy benzyl)-*p*-phenylene diamine (BDBPD) resin²⁴ it was the greater cavity size with four O-donors involved in metal chelation favouring selective extraction of U^{VI} and Th^{IV}. In *o*-vanillinsemicarbazone³⁵ there are three binding sites, one nitrogen and two oxygen atoms, which supposedly form two chelate rings (5- and 6-membered) making it a versatile reagent. Again 6,6,6-trifluoro-2,5-dioxo-4-(thiophene-2-carbonyl)hexyl phosphinic acid (TDHCHPA)⁵⁴ works well in acidic regions to near neutrality. Hence it is clearly seen that there is a continuous interest in synthesizing solid phase extractants with more flexible working conditions. These sorbents have been characterized by elemental analyses and instrumental techniques like FTIR and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

Optimum pH of adsorption :

In solid phase extraction studies, which involve chelation, influence of pH of the aqueous solution is one of the important factors for quantitative collection/

concentration and recoveries of target analytes. In general, formation of uranium species varies over the pH range. Uranium becomes increasingly hydrolyzed and forms oligomeric species with increasing pH. Many researchers reported that at $\text{pH} \leq 4.3$, uranium exists predominantly as monomeric species⁹⁹⁻¹⁰¹ viz. UO_2^{2+} , and small amount of $\text{UO}_2(\text{OH})^+$. When the $\text{pH} \geq 5$, the formation of colloidal or oligomeric species, i.e. $(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{OH})_2^{2+}$, $(\text{UO}_2)_3(\text{OH})_5^+$, $(\text{UO}_2)_4(\text{OH})_7^+$, $(\text{UO}_2)_3(\text{OH})_7^-$ are formed. Moreover, the precipitation of $\text{UO}_2(\text{OH})_2$ may occur.

Eluting agents :

For the recovery of uranium, thorium and the lanthanides usually hydrochloric acid and nitric acid of different strengths have been used as eluting agents. Some other commonly used eluting agents are $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ ^{27,28,30,33,49}, Na_2CO_3 ⁸⁶, EDTA^{48,54,66} and α -hydroxy isobutyric acid (α -HIBA)^{49,86}.

Na_2CO_3 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ solutions have been effectively used for stripping of U^{VI} and Th^{IV} . This is due

to the fact that U^{VI} and Th^{IV} form nonextractable and more stable anionic metal carbonato species viz. $[\text{UO}_2(\text{CO}_3)_3]^{4-}$, $[\text{Th}(\text{CO}_3)_5]^{6-}$, which are eluted from the resin phase. EDTA forms $[\text{M}(\text{EDTA})]^-$ or $[\text{M}(\text{EDTAH})]$ complexes with lanthanides and actinides, which are relatively more stable than the corresponding metal-polymer chelates. α -HIBA is known to be a very effective extractant for lanthanides and actinides. Thus, the separation of actinides and lanthanides could be achieved by using suitable eluting agents.

Preconcentration factors :

Since concentration of metals ions in natural water and other environmental samples is too low for their direct determination, preconcentration or enrichment step is unavoidable even with a sensitive method of detection. Typical preconcentration factors of the sorbents have been included in Table 2. Some of the exchangers show very high preconcentration factors – as high as 500^{38,42}. The others have moderate preconcentrating factors. The lowest preconcentration factor is seen for La^{III} with *o*-vanillinsemicarbazone³⁵.

Table 2. A glimpse of exchange capacities, pH range, preconcentration factors and $t_{1/2}$ values of typical solid phase extractants

Functional group [Ref.]	Exchange capacity (mmol g ⁻¹)	pH	Preconcentration factor	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
TAR [20]	U-0.71	4.0	-	5
TAN [21]	U-0.41	6.0	-	60
	Th-0.76	3.0	-	-
Tiron [22]	U-0.032	4.5-5.5	-	3.6
Quinalizarin [23]	U-9.20 × 10 ⁻³	5.0-6.0	-	6.3
(Bis-3,4-dihydroxybenzyl)- <i>p</i> - phenylenediamine [24]	U-0.666	6.5-7.0	350	1.5
	Th-0.664	7.0-7.7	350	1.6
TAM [25]	U-0.80	4.0	-	60
	Th-0.84	4.0	-	-
DBBT [26]	U-0.90	4.5-7.0	-	7
MOPPA [27]	U-1.45	1.0-6.5	400	3
	Th-1.39	2.0-6.5	333	4
	La-1.31	3.0-5.0	-	6
<i>N,N</i> -Dihexylcarbamoymethyl- phosphonic acid [28]	U-1.429	6.5	333	2.6
	Th-1.228	4.0	333	2.3
	La-1.356	4.0-5.0	400	2.1
(Bis-2,3,4-trihydroxybenzyl)ethylene- diamine [29]	U-1.43	4.0-5.0	-	2.6
	Th-1.19	1.0-2.0	-	2.7
3,4-Dihydroxybenzoylmethyl- phosphonic acid [30]	U-1.660	6.0-6.5	333	2.1
	Th-1.509	3.0-4.0	333	2.0
(Bis-2-hydroxybenzyl)- <i>p</i> -phenylene diamine [31]	U-1.68	6.0-6.5	400	2.5
	Th-1.62	6.0-6.5	450	2.3
ADHA [32]	U-0.692	1.0	-	<2.3

Table-2 (contd.)

[(2-Hydroxyarsinoylphenylamino)-methyl]phosphonic acid [33]	U-1.49	5.0-6.0	365	4.6
	Th-1.40	4.0-5.0	300	4.1
	La-1.12	1.0-3.0	270	7.4
Oxyacetone acetamide [34]	U-0.859	5.0-7.0	400	<5
	Th-0.797	3.0-4.0	400	
<i>o</i> -Vanillinsemicarbazone [35]	U-0.0121	6.0-8.0	120	6.5
	Th-0.139	3.0-4.5	125	5.0
	Ce-0.018	6.0-9.0	97	8.5
	La-0.016	6.0-9.0	95	9.0
Succinic acid [36]	U-0.0516	4.5-8.0	-	0.5
2,6-Diacetylpyridine	U-0.042	5.5	-	-
2,3-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde	U-0.062	7.0	-	-
2-Thiophenecarboxaldehyde [37]	U-0.081	6.5	-	-
Bicine [38]	U-0.38	7.64	500	-
	La-0.35	6.15	500	-
	Nd-0.40	7.58	500	-
	Tb-0.42	7.52	500	-
	Th-0.25	6.95	500	-
	U-0.0742	-	-	-
2,6-Diacetylpyridine [39]	U-0.0742	-	-	-
Humic acid [41]	Th-0.151	4.0	-	-
Malonic acid [42]	Th-0.083	5.0-8.0	500	10
Bis-2[(<i>o</i> -carbomethoxy)phenoxy]-ethylamine [43]	La-0.55	-	100	-
	Nd-0.62	-	100	-
	Sm-0.69	-	100	-
<i>p</i> -Tert-butylcalix[8]arene [44]	U-0.73	7.09	-	-
	Th-0.75	7.12	-	-
5-Aminoquinoline-8-ol [45]	U-11.5	4.0-6.0	200	2.4
Pyrogallol [46]	U-0.0282	5.5-6.2	-	2.8
EEBEHBA [48]	U-0.629	4 M	400	<3
	Th-0.214	[A]	267	-
Di-bis(2-ethylhexyl)-malonamide [49]	U-0.263	5 M	310	2.5
	Th-0.165	[A]	250	4.1
Quinoline-8-ol [51]	U-0.505	4.0-7.0	-	-
TTA [52]	U-0.014	-	-	-
2,2'-Dihydroxyazobenzene [53]	U-0.084	8.0	-	-
6,6,6-Trifluoro-2,5-dioxo-4-(thiophene-2-carbonyl)hexylphosphonic acid [54]	U-1.73	5.0-6.5	333	2.6
	Th-1.70	2.0-3.0	333	2.5
	Nd-1.40	1.0-3.0	267	3.9
	La-1.27	1.0-3.0	267	3.6
Calix[4]arene- <i>o</i> -vanillinsemicarbazone [57]	U-204.76	6.0-7.0	143	6.5
	Th-177.47	3.5-4.5	153	5
Calix[6]arene hydroxamic acid [58]	U-0.411	6.0	105	12
	Th-0.463	4.0	99	11
	Ce-0.395	7.5	107	12
	La-0.0135	6.5-8.0	125	10
Calix[4]arene semicarbazone [59]	U-0.0103	6.5-8.5	130	12.5

Table-2 (contd.)

	Th-0.0122	2.5-4.5	102	6.5
	U-0.0127	5.5-7.0	108	8.5
Serine [62]	U-0.21	3.0	-	-
3,4-Dihydroxybenzoic acid [64]	U-1.386	3.0-9.0	-	4
2-Amino-5-hydroxybenzoic acid [65]	-	7.0	-	-
CRC	U-0.050	4.0	-	120
CRCH [66]	U-0.034	4.0	-	150
Quinoline-8-o1 [67]	Th-0.086	5.0-7.0	-	-
Bis(2-ethylhexyl)methane-	U-0.612	1-3 M	-	-
diphosphonic [68]	Th-0.371	[A]	-	-
	Nd-0.314	-	-	-
DTPA [69]	La-0.748	6.0	-	-
	Th-1.85	-	-	-
5,7-Dichloroquinoline-8-o1 [77]	U-7.9 × 10 ⁻³	4.5-7.0	-	-
Dicyclohexano-18-crown-6 [78]	U-0.0102	-	-	-
CCS-HP/IDA [87]	La-0.34	5.0	-	-
Tulsion CH-90 [86]	Eu-0.31	5.3	-	60
	U-0.96	3.1	-	120
TOPO [91]	U-0.0169	-	-	-
Catechol [92]	U-0.0669	-	-	-
Diarylazobisphenol [93]	U-0.0771	-	-	-
Poly(acrylonitrile-co-divinylbenzene) [94]	U-0.858	-	-	119

Kinetics :

These developed sorbents have fast exchange kinetics even under optimum experimental conditions. These systems exhibit faster kinetics due to the presence of hydrophilic groups that increase the chelating site accessibility of metal ions by providing better surface contact with the aqueous phase. A glimpse at Table 2 gives us an idea of the fast kinetics involved. There are only a few exchangers for which we find that the $t_{1/2}$ is more than 60 min^{21,25,66,86,95}. This slow kinetics may be attributed to the inaccessibility of the active sites. There are a few reports with $t_{1/2}$ values in the range of 11-20 min while the rest is < 10 min. In case of succinic acid anchored on to XAD-4 it is 30 s³⁶.

Methods of detection

From the pie diagram (Fig. 1) it is seen that in most cases (39%) the method of detection is UV-Visible spectrophotometry. Atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) (8%), inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICPAES) (13%), inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) (13%), fluorimetry (13%) are also used for the detection of the 4f and 5f metal ions. Detection techniques such as X-ray fluores-

Fig. 1. Methods for the detection of 4f and 5f metals.

cence^{47,99}, radiotracer^{66,68,86}, and classical method like complexometric titration⁹⁵ etc. have also been used.

Spectrophotometry is a relatively simple method and a low cost instrument hence easily affordable compared to others. For spectrophotometric determination the commonly used chromogenic reagents are arsenazo(III) for uranium, thorium and Thoron for thorium.

AAS is very convenient and widespread, and has an acceptable level of accuracy for most analytes with a better precision. In case of ICPAES simultaneous multielemental detection is possible which has definite advantages over single element detection methodologies.

Now a days, ICP-MS has become one of the most powerful analytical techniques for trace element analysis with high sensitivity as well as with wide linear dynamic range and simultaneous multielement detection capability^{102,103}. Nevertheless, ICP-MS is extremely sensitive to matrix interferences induced by high salt contents (more than 1 g L⁻¹).

X-Ray fluorescence method has an added advantage over the other methods because it is a nondestructive method. But it is less sensitive and more expensive. Radioisotopes are widely used as tracers in analytical chemistry. An advantage of this method is that there is no chemical interference. But a severe drawback is that it cannot differentiate between the different chemical species of the same element.

Applications

To ascertain the practical applicability of the resins they were applied to various synthetic as well as real samples. The pie diagram (Fig. 2) shows that in most cases 4f and 5f metal ions have been separated from sea

Fig. 2. Applications of solid phase extractants towards the separation of 4f and 5f metals in various matrices.

water (24%), well water (11%) and monazite sand (11%). These metal ions have been separated from tap water (6%), river water (6%), soil and sediment (9%), radioactive wastes (6%), synthetic mixture of nuclear spent fuel composition (6%), geological samples (6%), rare earth chloride samples and synthetic mixtures (10%) also.

Extraction of uranium from sea water has attracted wide attention the world over in view of the anticipated depletion of uranium mineral resources in the near future. Though the concentration of uranium is extremely low, only 3 ng ml⁻¹, it constitutes a significant source due to the large quantity of sea water available⁵⁸. The adsorption method using solid adsorbents is promising for uranium recovery either from sea water or from uranium bearing effluents generated in the nuclear industry with regard to economic and environmental friendly aspects. Uranium has been separated from tap water, river water, well water, soil and sediment etc.

Separation of actinides and lanthanides from radioactive wastes is also a very common application. It is seen that in many cases lanthanides and actinides has been separated from synthetic mixture of nuclear spent fuel composition^{27,28,30,49}.

Thorium has been separated mostly from monazite sand^{24,27,34,59}. Lanthanides have been separated from geological samples, monazite sand, nuclear wastes, rare earth chloride samples and synthetic mixtures^{35,42,47,59,65}.

Analytical characteristics

The recoveries of the metal ions are almost quantitative (> 99%) in most cases (Table 3). Using serine diacetic acid⁶³ the limit of detection (LOD) for Th^{IV} has been found to be at sub ppb level whereas using 2-

Table 3. Typical analytical characteristics

Functional group [Ref.]	Analytical characteristics		
	Detection	RSD (%)	Recovery (%)
Tiron [22]	U-0.70 µg ml ⁻¹	-	-
Quinalizarin [22]	U-0.073 µg ml ⁻¹	-	-
(Bis-3,4-dihydroxybenzyl)- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine [24]	U-20 ng ml ⁻¹ Th-30 ng ml ⁻¹	< 2.8	> 99.5
DBBT [26]	U	2.4	96
MOPPA [27]	U-4 ng ml ⁻¹ LOQ Th-15 ng ml ⁻¹ LOQ La-20 ng ml ⁻¹ LOQ	- - -	99.9 99.8 99.5

Table-3 (contd.)

<i>N,N</i> -Dihexylcarbamoylmethylphosphonic acid [28]	U-10 ng ml ⁻¹	4.2	> 99.8
	Th-20 ng ml ⁻¹	-	-
	La-15 ng ml ⁻¹	-	-
(Bis-2,3,4-trihydroxybenzyl)ethylene-diamine [29]	U-5 ng ml ⁻¹	< 3.5	99.4
	Th-5 ng ml ⁻¹	-	98.9
3,4-Dihydroxybenzoylmethylphosphonic acid [30]	U-10 ng ml ⁻¹	3.9	99.9
	Th-10 ng ml ⁻¹	-	99.8
(Bis-2-hydroxybenzyl)- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine [31]	U-5 ng ml ⁻¹	≤ 2.5	> 99
	Th-10 ng ml ⁻¹	-	-
ADHA [32]	15 µg L ⁻¹ LOQ	-	-
[(2-Dihydroxyarsinoylphenylamino)-methyl]phosphonic acid [33]	U-23 ng ml ⁻¹	4.9	99.4
	Th-20 ng ml ⁻¹	-	99.8
	La-18 ng ml ⁻¹	-	99.3
Oxyacetone acetamide [34]	U-5.5 ng ml ⁻¹	< 4.1	98.9
	Th-5.2 ng ml ⁻¹	-	99.1
<i>o</i> -Vanillinsemicarbazone [35]	La	3.8	96-97
	Ce	3.6	96-97
	Th	2.2	98
	U	2.6	97-98
	U-2 µg ml ⁻¹	2.56	-
Succinic acid [36]	-	1.2	-
4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide	-	8.5	-
2,6-Diacetylpyridine	U	-	-
2,3-Dihydroxybenzaldehyde	-	-	-
2-Thiophene carboxaldehyde [37]	-	-	-
Bicine [38]	-	-	> 90
2,6-Diacetylpyridine [40]	U-0.067 µg L ⁻¹	-	-
Humic acid [41]	Th	2.7	96-99
Malonic acid [42]	Th-0.2 µg dm ⁻³	2.54	> 99
Bis-2-[(<i>o</i> -carbomethoxy)phenoxy]-ethylamine [43]	La ^{III} , Nd ^{III} , Sm ^{III}	-	99
5-Aminoquinoline-8-ol [45]	U-2 µg L ⁻¹	2.64	99.1
Pyrogallol [46]	U-0.066 µg L ⁻¹	-	-
Thorin [47]	Sm-13.8 µg L ⁻¹	-	100
	Eu-17 µg L ⁻¹	-	-
	Gd-15.7 µg L ⁻¹	-	-
EEBEHBA [48]	U-20 µg L ⁻¹	< 3.6	99
	Th-20 µg L ⁻¹	-	-
Di-bis(2-ethylhexyl)-malonamide [49]	U-20 ng ml ⁻¹	5.2	99.7
	Th-23 ng ml ⁻¹	-	99.3
TTA [50]	Th, U-22 µg dm ⁻³	-	-
TDHCHPA [54]	U-5 µg L ⁻¹ LOQ	3.9	99.8
	Th-10 µg L ⁻¹ LOQ	-	-
	Nd-10 µg L ⁻¹ LOQ	-	-
	La-15 µg L ⁻¹ LOQ	-	-
	U-6.14 µg L ⁻¹	1.7	98-98.5
Calix[4]arene- <i>o</i> -vanillinsemicarbazone [57]	Th-4.29 µg L ⁻¹	1.5	-

Table-3 (contd.)

Serine diacetic acid [63]	Th-sub ppb level	-	90-100
3,4-Dihydroxy benzoic acid [64]	-	-	96.3-105
2-Amino-5-hydroxy benzoic acid [65]	ppt to sub ppb level	-	-
Quinoline-8-o1 [67]	Th-2 $\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$	-	-
5,7-Dichloroquinoline-8-o1 [77]	U-2 ng ml^{-1}	1.5	-
Iminodiacetate [85]	U-0.5 ng L^{-1}	-	-
LOQ - limit of quantitation.			

amino-5-hydroxy benzoic acid⁶⁵ the LOD for various metals reported to be in the range of ppt to sub-ppb level. In both cases detection has been carried out by ICPAES method. In most cases the LOD lies between 5-10 ng ml^{-1} . Again relative standard deviation (RSD) values are in the range 2.4-5.2%.

Conclusion

From this literature survey it is evident that there has been an increasing interest in the synthesis of solid phase extractants. It is observed that the chelating resins have been primarily used for preconcentration and separation of 4f and 5f metal ions but chemical speciation has not been carried out. So there is plenty of scope to explore in this field of research. It is seen that classical methods of synthesis of chelating exchangers predominate. There is only one instance of environmental friendly microwave-assisted synthesis⁴³.

To conclude it can be said that solid phase extraction using functionalized chelating resins show a constant improvement of sensitivity and reliability of determination methods in a wide variety of samples ranging from geological samples to soil-sediment-sand, synthetic mixtures to nuclear wastes, tap water to sea water. More studies and applications of determination and separation of lanthanides and actinides using solid phase extractants will be helpful in recovering the high purity metals of importance.

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References

- M. Torre and M. L. Marina, *CRC Critical Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1994, **24**, 327.
- B. S. Garg, R. K. Sharma, N. Bhojak and S. Mittal, *Microchem. J.*, 1999, **61**, 94.
- K. L. Nash and M. P. Jensen, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 2001, **36**, 1257.
- B. C. Mondal, D. Das and A. K. Das, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2001, **450**, 223.
- B. C. Mondal, D. Das and A. K. Das, *Talanta*, 2002, **56**, 145.
- B. C. Mondal and A. K. Das, *React. Funct. Polym.*, 2002, **53**, 45.
- B. C. Mondal and A. K. Das, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2003, **477**, 73.
- D. Banerjee and A. K. Das, *Microchim. Acta*, 2003, **141**, 107.
- S. Dutta and A. K. Das, *Indian J. Chem. Tech.*, 2005, **12**, 139.
- C. J. Kantipuly and A. D. Westland, *Talanta*, 1988, **35**, 1.
- G. D. Clayton and F. E. Clayton (eds.), "Patty's Industrial Hygiene and Toxicology", 4th ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1994.
- "Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry", U. S. Public Health Service, Chapman and Hall, New York, 2000.
- A. P. Gilman, D. C. Villencube and V. E. Seccours, *Toxicol. Sci.*, 1998, **41**, 117.
- WHO : "Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality", 2nd ed., Addendum to Vol. 2 Health criteria and Other Supporting Information, WHO/EOS/98-1, Geneva, 1998, p. 283.
- WHO : "Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality", 3rd ed., 2000, p. 152.
- E. A. Huff, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1969, **27**, 229.
- H. Onoshi and K. Sekine, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 473.
- P. Thakur, V. Chakravorty, K. C. Dash, T. R. Ramamohan and M. L. P. Reddy, *Radiochim. Acta*, 1998, **80**, 155.
- D. I. Ryabchikov and E. K. Golbraikh, "The Analytical Chemistry of Thorium", Pergamon Press, New York, 1963.
- C. H. Lee, M. Y. Suh, J. S. Kim, D. Y. Kim, W. H. Kim and T. Y. Eom, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1999, **382**, 199.

21. W. Lee, S. E. Lee, C. H. Lee and Y. S. Kim, *Mikrochim. J.*, 2001, **70**, 195.
22. M. Kumar, D. P. S. Rathore and A. K. Singh, *Analyst*, 2000, **125**, 1221.
23. M. Kumar, D. P. S. Rathore and A. K. Singh, *Fresenius' J. Anal. Chem.*, 2001, **370**, 377.
24. D. Prabhakaran and M. S. Subramanian, *Talanta*, 2003, **61**, 423.
25. W. Lee, S. E. Lee, M. K. Kim, C. H. Lee and Y. S. Kim, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **23**, 1067.
26. M. Merdivan, M. Z. Düz and C. Hamamci, *Talanta*, 2001, **55**, 639.
27. C. S. K. Raju, S. Srinivasan and M. S. Subramanian, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 2005, **40**, 2213.
28. M. A. Maheswari and M. S. Subramanian, *Talanta*, 2004, **64**, 202.
29. D. Prabhakaran and M. S. Subramanian, *React. Funct. Polym.*, 2003, **57**, 147.
30. M. A. Maheswari and M. S. Subramanian, *React. Funct. Polym.*, 2005, **62**, 105.
31. M. A. Maheswari and M. S. Subramanian, *Anal. Lett.*, 2003, **36**, 2875.
32. M. A. Maheswari and M. S. Subramanian, *Solvent Ex. Ion Exchange*, 2005, **23**, 249.
33. D. Prabhakaran and M. S. Subramanian, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2004, **379**, 519.
34. D. Prabhakaran and M. S. Subramanian, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 2004, **39**, 941.
35. V. K. Jain, A. Handa, S. S. Sait, P. Shrivastav and Y. K. Agrawal, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2001, **429**, 237.
36. P. Metilda, K. Sanghamitra, J. M. Gladis, G. R. K. Naidu and T. Prasada Rao, *Talanta*, 2005, **65**, 192.
37. D. Kara, A. Fischer and S. J. Hill, *Analyst*, 2006, **131**, 1232.
38. K. Dew, R. Pathak and G. N. Rao, *Talanta*, 1999, **48**, 579.
39. N. Demirel, M. Merdivan, N. Pirinccioglu and C. Hamamci, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2003, **485**, 213.
40. D. Kara, A. Fischer and S. J. Hill, *Analyst*, 2005, **130**, 1518.
41. S. Erdogan, M. Merdivan, C. Hamamci, O. Akba and A. Baysal, *Anal. Lett.*, 2004, **37**, 2565.
42. P. Metilda, J. M. Gladis and T. Prasada Rao, *Radiochim. Acta*, 2004, **92**, 931.
43. H. Kaur and Y. K. Agrawal, *React. Funct. Polym.*, 2005, **65**, 277.
44. R. Pathak and G. N. Rao, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1996, **335**, 283.
45. J. M. Gladis and T. Prasada Rao, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2002, **373**, 867.
46. M. Kumar, D. P. S. Rathore and A. K. Singh, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 2001, **137**, 127.
47. I. E. Vito, A. N. Masi and R. A. Olsina, *Talanta*, 1999, **49**, 929.
48. M. A. Maheswari and M. S. Subramanian, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 2004, **39**, 3621.
49. D. Prabhakaran and M. S. Subramanian, *Talanta*, 2005, **65**, 179.
50. R. S. Praveen, P. Metilda, S. Daniel and T. Prasada Rao, *Talanta*, 2005, **67**, 960.
51. A. Jyo, S. Matsufune, H. Ono and H. Egawa, *J. Appl. Polym. Sc.*, 1997, **45**, 1327.
52. D. Prabhakaran and M. S. Subramanian, *Anal. Lett.*, 2003, **36**, 2277.
53. B. B. Jang, K. Lee, W. J. Kwon and J. Suh, *J. Polym. Sci. A : Polym. Chem.*, 1999, **37**, 3169.
54. M. A. Maheswari and M. S. Subramanian, *Anal. Lett.*, 2005, **38**, 1331.
55. K. Ueda, Y. Sato, O. Yoshimura and Y. Yamamoto, *Analyst*, 1988, **113**, 773.
56. C. Kantipuly, S. Karragadda, A. Chow and H. D. Gesser, *Talanta*, 1990, **37**, 491.
57. V. K. Jain, R. A. Pandya, S. G. Pillai and P. S. Srivastav, *Talanta*, 2006, **70**, 257.
58. U. V. Trivedi, S. K. Menon and Y. K. Agrawal, *React. Funct. Polym.*, 2002, **50**, 205.
59. V. K. Jain, A. Handa, R. Pandya, P. Shrivastav and Y. K. Agrawal, *React. Funct. Polym.*, 2002, **51**, 101.
60. A. Syamal, M. M. Singh and D. Kumar, *React. Funct. Polym.*, 1999, **39**, 27.
61. M. A. Hughes and E. Rosenberg, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 2007, **42**, 261.
62. K. Oshita, M. Oshima, Y. Gao, K. H. Lee and S. Motomizu, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2003, **480**, 239.
63. L. Hakim, A. Sabarudin, M. Oshima and S. Motomizu, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2007, **588**, 73.
64. A. Sabarudin, M. Oshima, T. Takayanagi, L. Hakim, K. Oshita, Y. H. Gao and S. Motomizu, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2007, **581**, 21.
65. P. Metilda, J. M. Gladis and T. Prasada Rao, *Radiochim. Acta*, 2003, **91**, 737.
66. S. Dutta, P. K. Mohapatra, S. P. Ramnani, S. Sabharwal, A. K. Das and V. K. Manchanda, *Desalination* (in press).
67. P. Metilda, J. M. Gladis and T. Prasada Rao, *Radiochim. Acta*, 2003, **91**, 737.
68. E. P. Horwitz, R. Chiarizia and M. L. Dietz, *React. Funct. Polym.*, 1997, **33**, 25.
69. D. K. Singh and R. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 447.
70. H. Kumagai, T. Yokoyama, T. M. Suzuki and T. Suzuki, *Analyst*, 1999, **124**, 1595.

71. M. Draye A. Favre-Réguillon, D. Wruck, I. Foos, A. Guy and K. Czerwinski, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 2000, **36**, 899.
72. S. Samal, R. R. Das, N. K. Mohapatra, S. Acharya and R. K. Dey, *J. Appl. Polym. Sc.*, 2000, **77**, 3128.
73. Z. Su, G. Zhan, X. Luo and Q. Pu, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1995, **310**, 493.
74. E. Bou-Maroun, G. I. Goetz-Grandmont and A. Boos, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 2006, **41**, 2933.
75. M. Ahuja, S. Gupta and P. N. Mathur, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 1995, **12**, 257.
76. B. L. Rivas, H. A. Matúrana and S. Villegas, *J. Appl. Polym. Sc.*, 2000, **77**, 1994.
77. I. M. Gladis and T. Prasada Rao, *Anal. Lett.*, 2002, **35**, 501.
78. C. R. Preetha and T. Prasada Rao, *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.*, 2006, **267**, 265.
79. P. Metilda, I. M. Gladis and T. Prasada Rao, *Radiochim. Acta*, 2005, **93**, 219.
80. S. Pal, V. Ramachandhran, S. Prabhakar, P. K. Tewari and M. Sudersanan, *J. Macromol. Sc., Part A Pure and Appl. Chem.*, 2006, **43**, 735.
81. I. M. Ismail, M. Nogami and K. Suzuki, *Solvent Extr. Ion Exch.*, 2003, **21**, 465.
82. M. Pesavento, R. Biesuz, G. Alberti and M. Sturini, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2003, **376**, 1023.
83. D. Rahmi, Y. Zhu, E. Fujimori, T. Umemura and H. Haraguchi, *Talanta*, 2007, **72**, 600.
84. Y. Gao, K. Oshita, K. H. Lee, M. Oshima and S. Motomizu, *Analyst*, 2002, **127**, 1713.
85. M. Nicolai, C. Rosin, N. Tousset and Y. Nicolai, *Talanta*, 1999, **50**, 433.
86. S. Dutta, P. K. Mohapatra, G. D. Dhekane, A. K. Das and V. K. Manchanda, *Desalination* (in press).
87. K. H. Lee, M. Oshima and S. Motomizu, *Analyst*, 2002, **127**, 769.
88. H. Bag, M. Jale and A. R. Tezker, *Fresenius J. Anal. Chem.*, 1999, **366**, 224.
89. O. Abollino, C. Sarzini, E. Mentasti and L. Mheratore, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1993, **49**, 1411.
90. A. Zhang, G. Uchiyama and T. Asakura, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 2003, **38**, 1829.
91. A. M. Starwin and T. Prasada Rao, *Talanta*, 2004, **63**, 225.
92. A. Zhang, G. Uchiyama and T. Asakura, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 2003, **38**, 1829.
93. M. Shamsipur, A. R. Ghiasvand and Y. Yamini, *Anal. Chem.*, 1999, **71**, 4892.
94. N. Kabay and H. Egawa, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 1993, **28**, 1985.
95. F. A. Alakhras, K. A. Darı and M. S. Mubarak, *J. Appl. Polym. Sc.*, 2005, **97**, 691.
96. T. Sakaguchi and A. Nakajima, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 1994, **29**, 205.
97. M. S. Decarvalho, M. D. F. Domingues, J. L. Mantovano and J. W. S. D. Dacunha, *Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.*, 2002, **253**, 253.
98. K. A. K. Ebraheem, M. S. Mubarak, Z. J. Yassien and F. Khalili, *Sepr. Sc. Technol.*, 2000, **35**, 2115.
99. A. A. Aita, *Hydrometallurgy*, 2005, **80**, 13.
100. A. Froideval, M. D. Nero, R. Barillon, J. Hommet and G. Mignot, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2003, **266**, 221.
101. C. J. Chrisholm-Brause, J. M. Berge, R. A. Matzner and D. E. Morris, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2001, **233**, 38.
102. H. Haraguchi, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2004, **16**, 5.
103. H. Haraguchi, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1999, **72**, 1163.